

ON THE ATOMIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF DIVALENT COPPER.

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The susceptibilities of the various cupric salts were measured with the help of Gouy's balance. The sample was placed in a tube between the poles of a strong electro-magnet and the force exerted by the magnet was measured by means of an analytical balance. In those cases, in which the measurements had to be taken at various temperatures, a furnace made of nichrome wire on mica plates was placed between the poles of the magnet and the balance was standardised separately for every temperature employed. The temperatures were taken by a standard thermometer reading tenths of a degree Centigrade.

Cupric Fluoride (anhydrous).

Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_A \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_A$		C_m	μ	θ
				Obs.	Calc.			
305.5°K	15.191	1542.9	1554.9	643.13	643.13	0.4052	1.80	+45.6
328.4	14.004	1422.4	1434.4	697.15	697.12			
347.5	13.135	1334.1	1346.1	743.45	744.03			
368.2	12.258	1246.3	1258.3	794.73	794.50			
383.0	11.725	1190.9	1202.9	831.32	831.21			
403.0	11.062	1123.5	1135.5	881.04	881.04			

The reduction of the molar susceptibility to the atomic one for copper was done by deducting Pascal's value (*cf.* Stoner, "Magnetism and Matter", 1934, p. 470) of -6×10^{-6} for fluorine. The perfect agreement between the measured atomic susceptibilities and the calculated ones show that the Weiss-Curie law is strictly obeyed.

The Curie temperature is $\theta = +45.6^\circ\text{K}$, the Curie constant is 0.4052, giving 1.8 Bohr magnetons for copper in CuF_2 .

Cupric Hydro-arsenite.

Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_A \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_A$		C.	μ	θ
				Obs.	Calc.			
304.5°K	6.827	1280.4	1334.5	749.34	749.34	0.4956	2.00	-67.0
328.3	6.401	1200.5	1254.6	797.08	797.36			
336.1	6.282	1178.1	1232.2	811.56	813.10			
347.5	6.090	1142.0	1196.1	836.04	836.10			
357.2	5.949	1115.6	1169.7	854.89	855.66			
368.1	5.787	1085.3	1139.4	877.66	877.66			

The atomic susceptibility was obtained from the molar one by employing Kido's value (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1933, **22**, 835) of -51.20×10^{-6} for the arsenite radical and Pascal's value (*loc. cit.*) of -2.95×10^{-6} for hydrogen. The observed and the calculated values are again in accord with each other. The Curie temperature is $\theta = -67.0^\circ\text{K}$, the Curie constant, 0.4956, corresponding to 2.0 Bohr magnetons.

Cupric Ortho-arsenate.

Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_A \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_A$		C.	μ	θ
				Obs.	Calc.			
304.3°K	7.593	4105.5	1423.0	702.48	702.48	0.4695	1.945	-24.3
328.1	7.062	3818.5	1327.9	753.05	753.17			
335.9	6.908	3734.9	1300.1	769.18	769.79			
347.3	6.681	3612.5	1259.3	794.08	794.07			
358.3	6.490	3509.1	1224.8	816.45	817.50			
368.4	6.307	3410.3	1191.9	839.02	839.02			

The molar susceptibility was reduced to the atomic one with the help of Kido's value (*loc. cit.*) of -56.7×10^{-6} for the arsenate radical and Pascal's value of -13.0×10^{-6} (*loc. cit.*) for the water of crystallization. The Curie temperature is $\theta = -24.3^\circ\text{K}$, the Curie constant, 0.4695, from which $\mu = 1.95$ Bohr magnetons.

Other Cupric Compounds.

The following cupric salts were measured at only one temperature (17C°) in order to obtain their magneton numbers; measurements at several temperatures were not possible, because the salts decomposed. Effective magneton numbers were calculated under the assumption of the validity of Curie's law. The values obtained from the various compounds are in as good an accord with each other as can be expected under the circumstances.

Compound.	Temp.	$\chi \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_{eff} .
$\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$	290°K	8.80	1351.6	1385.6	1.80
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{KCl}$	290	4.75	1347.1	1464.2	1.85
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	290	5.31	1473.5	1608.1	1.94
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$.	290	8.27	1394.0	1463.0	1.85
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	290	5.70	1400.9	1505.1	1.88
$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$	290	5.62	1437.1	1523.1	1.89

The compounds investigated are most probably all of them co-valent, but for the following discussion this is immaterial; the situation is precisely the same for electro-valent or co-valent linkage.

Two of the electrons of the copper atom form diamagnetic combinations with the valency electrons of the negative radical, and the resulting paramagnetism is due to a core of the copper atom with 27 electrons in $d^9 \ ^3D_5/2$.

Theoretically (Van Vleck, "Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford, 1932, Chapter XI) the number of Bohr magnetons should be given by the equation,

$$\mu = \sqrt{4S(S+1) + L(L+1)}$$

from which for a 2D term $\mu = 3.0$ Bohr magnetons. On the other hand, if according to Van Vleck's theory the orbital moment is quenched, one should obtain

$$\mu = \sqrt{4S(S+1)}$$

which yields $\mu = 1.73$ Bohr magnetons.

The values obtained here vary between 1.8 and 2.0 magnetons. In consideration of the fact that some uncertainty as regards the correction due to the negative radical cannot be avoided, these values are in a good enough agreement with each other and show, that in the case of cupric salts the orbital magnetic moment is almost completely quenched and that in accordance with the results of Klemm and Schüth (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1932, **38**, 621) there is no difference in the magnetic state of the copper atom either in simple or in complex compounds. At the same time the values are fully in accord with those obtained by other authors (cf. table in Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 164).

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